

DISASTER PREPAREDNESS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN COASTAL DISTRICT OF THE BATANGAS CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on identifying the level of disaster preparedness of elementary schools in Coastal District of the Division of Batangas City. The variables considered were the of the conduct of activities on disaster preparedness in terms of earthquake, fire, landslide and typhoon. The study also identified the assessment of the respondents' involvement in the conduct of activities on disaster preparedness in relation to earthquake, fire, landslide and typhoon. This study also identified the constraints encountered in the conduct of activities for disaster preparedness. At the end of the study, an action plan was then formulated. The descriptive method of research was adopted with the aid of a researcher-made questionnaire as the primary tool in gathering data. Seventy- seven teachers served as the respondents of the study. Based from the findings of the study, most of the teacher-respondents conduct activities to a very great extent in terms of disaster preparedness. The teachers were greatly involved in the preparation and crafting of an effective contingency plan. Majority of the teacher respondents slightly disagree on the presented constraints in the preparation and execution of the activities for disaster preparedness. The output of the study was a proposed action plan that could help the school and the community especially the pupils and the teachers by providing them a variety of activities, projects and information about the proper responses, preparation and mitigation in terms of disaster.

Keywords: disaster preparedness, elementary schools, natural disaster, involvement